

Challenges of Implementation of Entrepreneurship-Oriented Animal Husbandry Curriculum in Senior Secondary Schools in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the challenges associated with implementing the entrepreneurship education (animal husbandry) curriculum in senior secondary schools within the Nsukka Education Zone of Enugu State. A descriptive survey research design was adopted, guided by two research questions and two hypotheses. The population of the study was all 24 respondents which include 16 animal husbandry teachers and 8 school principals. They were all used due to the manageable population size. Instrument used was Questionnaire on the Perception of Teachers and Principals on Implementing Animal Husbandry Curriculum (QPTPIAHC) with strong reliability indices (overall Cronbach Alpha = 0.877). Mean and standard deviation were used to analyze the research questions, while independent samples t-test at the 0.05 significance level tested the hypotheses. Findings revealed that major challenges included inadequate instructional materials and facilities, poor conceptualization of the curriculum, and insufficient professional development opportunities for teachers (teachers (M=2.96, SD=.56) and principal (M=.2.89, SD=.19)). Both teachers and principals agreed on strategies for improvement, such as supportive government policies, regular electricity supply for school farms, and collaboration with external livestock farmers based on the grand mean for teachers (M=3.59, SD=.43) and principals (M=3.56, SD=.33). Also the result $t(.1757) = .197^*$, $p = .85$ indicates that there was no significant difference in the mean response of teachers and principals on the strategies for effective implementation of animal husbandry curriculum. The study recommended increased provision of instructional resources and stronger school and industry linkages to enhance effective implementation animal husbandry curriculum.

Keywords: *Entrepreneurship Education, Animal Husbandry, Curriculum Implementation, Instructional Challenges, Secondary Education.*

INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurship education in animal husbandry was introduced into the senior secondary school curriculum as a strategic response to youth unemployment and the need for practical agricultural skill acquisition in Nigeria. However, the challenges of implementation of entrepreneurship curriculum have almost watered down the purpose of integrating entrepreneurship curriculum into the senior secondary school curriculum in Nigeria, which is to equip senior secondary school students with necessary skills, competences and attitude that will enable them create jobs for self-reliance. This means that the challenges of entrepreneurship education in Nigerian senior secondary school are numerous. These challenges according to Igbokwe-Ibeto, Agbdike and Osakede (2018) include poor infrastructure, lack of qualified teachers, limited resources and unclear instructional approach. Ruseva, Baltova, and Nikolova, (2024) added that limited teaching material and resources are part of the challenges of entrepreneurship education in senior secondary school in Nigeria. For

the sake of realization of the purpose of integrating entrepreneurship education into senior secondary school curriculum, strategies should be put in place by the government, school administration and education stakeholders to address these challenges.

Entrepreneurship education is the process of teaching and training that gives the student information, abilities, and entrepreneurial mindset that enables them to start and run a business. Egwuekwe, Eneh, and Eze (2020) define entrepreneurship education as the process of helping people develop their entrepreneurial abilities. and correct application of the skills in handling a business in other to make a difference in business sector. Entrepreneurship education is designed to empower students and young people by providing them with knowledge, skills, ideas, capabilities, and drive to start and effectively operate their own businesses for self-reliance. In Nigeria, 34 entrepreneurship subjects are taught in the secondary school which animal husbandry is one of them.

Animal husbandry is a branch of agriculture that focuses on animals that are raised for meat, milk, eggs and other things that could be got from animals. Animal husbandry involves the care of animals like housing, feeding, health care selective breeding, proper feeding and giving medical attention to the livestock. Effective teaching of animal husbandry will help students to be more knowledgeable in animal husbandry. They can start off livestock farming on graduation and they can also educate the farmers in the society better on animal husbandry. This will help in creating more employment opportunities, so they can employ themselves and also employ others, hence improving the economy of the nation. Animal husbandry is one of the entrepreneurship subjects in senior secondary school curriculum in Nigeria.

The senior secondary school level, which has a duration of three years, is where some students terminate their education, having obtained the senior secondary school certificate or continue their education depending on individual's capacity and choice. Hence, the inclusion of entrepreneurial subjects in the curriculum and the need to investigate the extent of implementation of these entrepreneurial subjects at this educational level. It is expected that when a student passes through senior secondary school, having been taught the entrepreneurship subjects, the student would be able to acquire at least a skill or two that would be useful for them in life. Hence effective implementation of animal husbandry curriculum will enable senior secondary school leavers to obtain skills in animal husbandry that will make them employable or employers of labour. Effectiveness of a planned curriculum lies in the implementation. There are many things challenging the effective implementation of entrepreneurship curriculum.

Challenges of curriculum implementation are those things that hinder or make it difficult for curriculum to be implemented effectively. Challenges of implementation of entrepreneurship curriculum in senior secondary school abound. Obilo, Akachukwu and Umeh (2017) who discovered that fund, overcrowded curriculum, none involvement of teachers in educational decision making, are challenges of implementing curriculum in schools. Also, inadequate human and material resources is one of the major challenges of implementation of entrepreneurship education in secondary school (Ogoamaka and Onyeagbako (2017). In addition, Akubilo (2002) contends that another challenge of entrepreneurship curriculum implementation is gender disparity. Some people forbid a particular gender from one activity or the other and if such activities are in the curriculum, implementation becomes a problem. Odey and Opoh (2015) are of the view that some of the challenges of curriculum implementation are inability of teachers to teach with ICT and lack of fund. However, Sa'ad and Usman (2014) see the challenges of curriculum implementation as inadequate qualified

teachers and under provision of instructional materials. On the other hand, Ibenegbu (2019) believes that school environment affects curriculum implementation. While Kanario and Mse (2016) said that teacher centred teaching approach do not encourage active participation of the learners which affects curriculum implementation negatively...

In another work, Obasi and Obih (2017) enumerated the things that hinder effective curriculum implementation as gender stereotype contents, inadequate textual material and inadequate teaching methods. According to Tsudo (2012), one of the ways of improving students' skill acquisition in secondary school is by allocating adequate time in the time table for practical works. Alade (2017) further enumerated some problems of implementation of innovation in the curriculum as, inadequate funding, overcrowded classroom, lack of adequate maintenance of buildings and equipment, facilities. In addition, Ali and Ajibola (2015) enumerated some challenges that militate against effective curriculum implementation as: inadequate instructional facilities, inadequate qualified teachers, poor funding syndrome, insufficient instructional materials, non-involvement of teachers in curriculum planning and decision making, lack of motivation. Proper curriculum planning is seriously challenged with poor implementation. Hence, Bolureanu, Mariuca, Bercu, Bedruce-Grigorut and Bedureanu (2020) is of the view that entrepreneurship learning can be facilitated through learners having role models, according to them this will stimulate the learners' confidence to start a business and make them desire entrepreneurship increase. Esmi, and Maben (2015) revealed that capable teachers should be employed to teach entrepreneurship education curriculum in schools, for qualified teachers will produce capable graduates with employable skills.

Ali and Ajibola (2015) suggested some strategies for effective curriculum implementation as: stake holders in education should jointly provide needed facilities and funds to schools, seminars and workshops should be organized for teachers so that they will understand the new curriculum and also be knowledgeable in the use of locally made instructional materials. Also, teachers should be involved in curriculum planning and educational decision making. The authors further advocated for improvement of teachers' salaries and governments sponsoring teachers for in-service training. Filado (2019) suggested adequate provision of instructional materials as a strategy for improving the teaching and learning of entrepreneurship education curriculum, and that when learners are trained without facilities, they find it difficult to practice after graduation.

From the above review, entrepreneurship education, particularly in the area of animal husbandry, was introduced into the senior secondary school curriculum to equip students with practical skills, self-reliance, and employable competencies in livestock production. However, despite its strategic importance in promoting agricultural development and youth empowerment, there are growing concerns about the effective implementation of the animal husbandry curriculum in public secondary schools within the Nsukka Education Zone of Enugu State.

Evidence suggests that students may not be acquiring the expected practical competencies, raising questions about possible constraints affecting curriculum delivery. These concerns point to potential issues such as inadequate instructional materials and facilities, insufficient teacher preparation and professional development, weak school-industry linkages, and limited administrative support. The problem of this study, therefore, is to determine the specific challenges hindering the effective implementation of the animal husbandry curriculum in senior secondary schools in Nsukka Education Zone and to identify strategies that could enhance its successful teaching and learning.

Specifically, the study sought to investigate teachers' and principals' perceptions on challenges teachers face in implementing animal husbandry curriculum as well as teachers' and principals' perceptions on strategies that could be put in place for effective implementation of animal husbandry curriculum.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research questions have been posed to guide this study:

- 1) What are the perceptions of teachers and principals on challenges of implementing animal husbandry curriculum in senior secondary school in Nsukka Education Zone?
- 2) What are the perceptions of teachers and principals on strategies that could be put in place for effective implementation of animal husbandry curriculum in senior secondary schools in Nsukka Education Zone?

Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of teachers and principals on the perceived challenges of effective implementation of animal husbandry curriculum in senior secondary school in Nsukka Education Zone.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of teachers and principals on the strategies for effective implementation of animal husbandry curriculum in senior secondary schools in Nsukka Education Zone.

METHODS

The study adopted the descriptive survey research design and it was carried out in Nsukka Education zone of Enugu state, Nigeria. The population of this study was 24 respondents, which comprised all the 16 animal husbandry teachers in public secondary schools in Nsukka Education Zone and all the eight principals of eight public secondary schools that offer animal husbandry in Nsukka Education Zone. Total population was used as sample for the study because the number is manageable.

A questionnaire was used for data collection. It is made up of two sections (A&B). Section A contains the demographic information of the respondents while section B has two clusters, cluster 1 on challenges of implementing animal husbandry curriculum has 12 items. Cluster 2 has 10 items on strategies for improving the implementation of animal husbandry curriculum implementation.

The questionnaire was structured using 4-point rating scale of SA = Strongly Agree (4); A = Agree (3); D = Disagree (2), SD = Strongly Disagree (1). The instrument used was Questionnaire on the Perception of Teachers and Principals on Implementing Animal Husbandry Curriculum (QPTPIAHC). It was face validated by three experts at the University of Nigeria, Nsukka with overall reliability index of 0.88 ascertained using Cronbach's alpha.

The questionnaire was personally administered by the researcher and collected immediately after the respondents had filled them. The data gathered was analysed using mean and standard deviation. A criterion mean of 2.50 was used for making remarks on the research questions and hypotheses were tested using an independent sample t-test, at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULT

Research Question One: What is the perception of teachers and principals on challenges of implementing animal husbandry curriculum in senior secondary school?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Perception of Teachers and Principals on Challenges of Implementing Animal Husbandry Curriculum

S/N	Challenges of implementation	Teachers n=16		Principals n= 8		Overall N=24		DEC
		\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}	SD	
1	Lack of competent teachers to teach animal husbandry	2.44	1.21	2.13	.835	2.33	1.09	D
2	Lack of qualified teachers	2.25	1.13	2.75	.835	2.42	1.06	D
3	Lack of adequate instructional facilities/materials	3.31	1.01	2.31	1.01	3.00	1.03	A
4	Poor conceptualization of animal husbandry curriculum by teachers	3.00	1.03	3.38	.518	3.12	.90	A
5	Insecure environment for animal husbandry	3.13	.957	3.33	.354	3.38	.88	A
6	Poor governmental financial support	3.33	.90	3.50	1.06	3.39	.94	A
7	Lack of in -service training, conferences, and workshops for teachers	3.38	1.09	3.00	.93	2.92	1.21	A
8	Inadequate time allocation in the time table for teaching animal husbandry curriculum	2.26	1.21	2.03	.641	2.15	1.07	D
9	Too much focus on certificates so students cannot risk their time in practical activities	3.38	.50	2.63	.744	3.15	.60	A
10	Lack of interest on the side of the students	3.00	.97	2.38	.916	2.79	.98	A
11	Poor teacher preparation towards teaching animal husbandry.	2.38	1.29	3.25	.46	2.67	1.09	A
12	Inconsistence in governmental education policies	3.38	.99	3.25	.86	3.33	.87	A
	Grand Total	2.96	.56	2.89	.19	2.93	.47	A

The result from Table 1 revealed the mean and standard deviation of teachers' and principals on the perceived challenges of implementation of animal husbandry curriculum in Nsukka Education Zone of Enugu state, Nigeria. Items 3-7,9 -12, shows their agreement to the items listed as challenges. While items 1,2, and 8 show their disagreement to the items as challenges as reflected in table 10. Results based on grand mean for teachers (M=2.96, SD=.56) and principal (M=2.89, SD=.19) indicates that both agreed that Lack of adequate instructional facilities/materials and poor conceptualization of animal husbandry curriculum by teachers are challenges of implementing animal husbandry curriculum.

HO₁: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of teachers and principals on the challenges of effective implementation of animal husbandry curriculum.

Table 2: An Independent Sample t-test Analysis of Perception of Teachers and Principals on the Challenges of Effective Implementation of Animal Husbandry Curriculum

Status sig	n	Mean	SD	t	df	p-value
Teachers	16	2.96	.56	.350*	22	.73
Principal	8	2.89	.19			
Total	24	2.93	.47			

*Significant at p < 0.05

Result presented in Table 2 is an independent sample t-test analysis of mean perception of teachers and principals on challenges of effective implementation of animal husbandry curriculum. The result of the analyses showed $t(22) = 350^*$, $p = .73$. Hence the null hypothesis was not rejected because $p > 0.05$. The result shows that there is no significant difference in the mean perception of teachers and principals on the challenges of implementation of animal husbandry curriculum.

Research Question Two: What is the perception of teachers and principals on strategies that could be put in place for effective implementation of animal husbandry curriculum in senior secondary schools in Nsukka Education Zone?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of Perception of Teachers and Principals on Strategies that could be put in place for Effective Implementation of Animal Husbandry Curriculum

S/N	Item description	Teachers n=16		Principals n=8		Overall 24		DEC
		\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}	SD	
1	Polices that should encourage animal husbandry should be made by the legislatures	3.63	.62	3.75	.463	3.67	.57	A
2	The school administration should provide regular supply of electricity in school/farms	3.56	.51	3.38	1.06	3.50	.72	A
3	Sufficient time should be allocated to animal husbandry in the time table	3.38	.81	4.00	.00	3.50	.72	A
4	Teaching of animal husbandry in schools should be linked with various livestock farmers outside school	3.38	1.03	3.75	.463	3.50	.89	A
5	Teachers should be sent for in-service training to be knowledgeable on teaching animal husbandry	3.63	.50	3.75	.463	3.67	.48	A
6	Government, private and public partnership should be used to provide the facilities and equipment needed for teaching animal husbandry	3.63	.50	3.63	.518	3.63	.50	A
7	Teaching of animal husbandry should be hands-on not theoretical based	3.69	.48	3.50	.736	3.63	.56	A
8	Regular workshops should be organized for animal husbandry teachers by school administration.	3.69	.60	3.08	.354	3.75	.53	A
9	Regular conferences and seminars should be organized for animal husbandry teachers by ministry of education.	3.75	.58	3.13	.835	3.54	.72	A
10	School management should encourage both staff and students of animal husbandry by giving them incentives	3.63	.50	2.88	1.23	3.37	.82	A
	Grand Mean	3.59	.43	3.56	.33	3.90	.36	A

The result from Table 3 shows the mean and standard deviation of perception of teachers and principals on strategies for effective implementation of animal husbandry curriculum in Nsukka Education Zone of Enugu state, Nigeria. The result shows that both teachers and principal strongly agree that from items 1 – 9 with mean range of 3.50 – 4.00 and corresponding standard deviation are strategies for improvement. Result based on the grand mean for teachers

($M=3.59$, $SD=.43$) and principals ($M=3.56$, $SD=.33$) shows that all the strategies in table 3 can be employed for improvement.

HO₂: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of teachers and principals on the strategies for effective implementation of animal husbandry curriculum.

Table 4: An Independent Sample t-test Analysis of Perception of Teachers and Principals on the Strategies for Effective Implementation of Animal Husbandry Curriculum

Status	n	Mean	SD	t	df	p-value
Teachers	16	3.59	.43	.197*	22	.835
Principal	8	3.56	.33			
Total	24	3.56	.39			
Significant at $p < 0.05$						

The result in table 4 shows $t(.1757) = .197^*$, $p = .85$. This result indicates that there is no significant difference in the mean response of teachers and principals on the strategies for effective implementation of animal husbandry curriculum. So, teachers are in agreement with the principals that these strategies could be employed for effective implementation of animal husbandry curriculum.

DISCUSSION

The findings revealed that both teachers and principals agreed that major challenges confronting the implementation of the animal husbandry curriculum in senior secondary schools in Nsukka Education Zone include inadequate instructional materials and facilities, poor conceptualization of the curriculum by teachers, insecure school environments, lack of in-service training, and limited opportunities for conferences and workshops. There was no significant difference in the mean perceptions of teachers and principals regarding these challenges, indicating a shared understanding of the implementation constraints. The finding on inadequate instructional materials is consistent with Ogoamaka and Onyeagbako (2017) and Sa'ad and Usman (2014), who reported that insufficient human and material resources constitute major barriers to curriculum implementation.

It also aligns with Obilo, Akachukwu, and Umeh (2017), who identified funding constraints, overcrowded curricula, and limited teacher involvement in educational decision-making as critical challenges. The finding of poor teacher preparation converges with Odey and Opoh (2015), who observed teachers' inability to effectively utilize ICT as a limitation to modern instructional delivery. Similarly, the issue of an insecure school environment supports Ibenegbu (2018), who noted that environmental factors significantly influence curriculum implementation. However, the finding that qualified teachers are available diverges from Sa'ad and Usman (2014), who reported inadequate qualified teachers as a challenge.

Regarding improvement strategies, teachers and principals strongly agreed that effective implementation requires supportive legislative policies, regular electricity supply for school farms, sufficient timetable allocation, linkage with livestock farmers outside the school, and in-service training for teachers, adoption of hands-on instructional approaches, regular workshops, seminars, and conferences, and incentive systems to motivate teachers and students. The finding corroborate with Kanorio and Mse (2016) and Esene and Maben (2015), who emphasized experiential learning in entrepreneurship education. The recommendation for school–industry linkage supports Ogoamaka and Onyeagbako (2017), who advocated robust

collaboration between schools and established enterprises. Furthermore, the allocation of sufficient instructional time concurs with Tsudo (2012), who highlighted adequate time as essential for effective skill acquisition. Overall, the consensus between teachers and principals suggests that addressing these identified challenges through coordinated policy support, professional development, infrastructural improvement, and practical-oriented instruction could significantly enhance the implementation of the animal husbandry curriculum in the Nsukka Education Zone.

CONCLUSION

This study concludes that the effective implementation of the animal husbandry curriculum in senior secondary schools within the Nsukka Education Zone is significantly constrained by multiple systemic and pedagogical challenges. These include inadequate instructional materials and facilities, poor teacher conceptualization of the curriculum, insecure school environments, and excessive emphasis on certification over skill acquisition, low student interest, inadequate teacher preparation, and overreliance on traditional teaching methods rather than experiential approaches.

Thus, addressing these interrelated factors is essential for revitalizing the animal husbandry curriculum and ensuring that it fulfills its intended goal of equipping students with practical entrepreneurial and agricultural competencies.

Recommendation

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made

- 1) Government and school administration should organize in-service training, seminars and workshops as well as provide occasional supervision of teaching / learning of animal husbandry
- 2) School administration should link animal husbandry teaching with livestock farmers outside school.
- 3) There should be a combined effort of the government and the school administration to provide adequate security and electricity in schools.
- 4) The school administration should allocate adequate time in the time table for teaching and learning of animal husbandry.

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